

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects
hash://md5/1696327f846f21ab03d7b90b2aeb54c8

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
review@globalbioticinteractions.org
<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects, has fingerprint hash://md5/1696327f846f21ab03d7b90b2aeb54c8, is 115MiB in size and contains 14,517 interactions with 7 unique types of associations (e.g., adjacentTo) between 1,976 primary taxa (e.g., Ixodidae Koch, 1844) and 2,406 associated taxa (e.g., 2c77dc27-d40d-450e-a5e9-2078ad9d2884). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Illinois Natural History Survey Insect Collection <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/inh-insects/archive/2473178936cd0d3107b043276a6e75df9c4575b1.zip>
 2026-06-02T16:04:29.101Z hash://md5/1696327f846f21ab03d7b90b2aeb54c8

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11

tool name	version
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 115MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects \
  | nomer append col \
  > name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/inhs-insects`, has fingerprint hash://md5/1696327f846f21ab03d7b90b2aeb54c8, is 115MiB in size and contains 14,517 interactions with 7 unique types of associations (e.g., `adjacentTo`) between 1,976 primary taxa (e.g., `Ixodidae Koch, 1844`) and 2,406 associated taxa (e.g., `2c77dc27-d40d-450e-a5e9-2078ad9d2884`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Eutarsopolipus	interactsWith	Stenolophus lecontei (Chaudoir, 1868)	Theodore Henry Frison R.D. Glasgow
Stenolophus lecontei (Chaudoir, 1868)	interactsWith	Eutarsopolipus	Theodore Henry Frison R.D. Glasgow
Eutarsopolipus brevichelus Husband & Husband, 2003	interactsWith	Stenolophus lecontei (Chaudoir, 1868)	Lantirn
Stenolophus lecontei (Chaudoir, 1868)	interactsWith	Eutarsopolipus brevichelus Husband & Husband, 2003	Lantirn

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
adjacentTo	7027
interactsWith	4393
hasHost	2878
visitsFlowersOf	147
eats	46
preysOn	17
preyedUponBy	9

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Ixodidae Koch, 1844	735
Dermacentor variabilis (Say, 1821)	550
Haemaphysalis leporispalustris (Packard, 1869)	277
Hymenoptera	269
Pulicidae Billberg, 1820	268
Mezira granulata (Say, 1832)	258
Phthiraptera Haeckel, 1896	208

sourceTaxonName	count
Psammotettix	202
Hypera brunniipennis (Boheman, 1834)	197
Siphonaptera	153
Chalcidoidea	147
Psyllidae Latreille, 1807	141
Myrsidea interrupta (Osborn, 1896)	126
Empoasca	125
Philopteridae	119
Orchopeas howardi (Baker, 1895)	118
Trombiculidae Ewing, 1929	108
Ichneumonidae	103
Ptinidae Latreille, 1802	98

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
2c77dc27-d40d-450e-a5e9-2078ad9d2884	686
under	617
Soybeans	584
2f6ddf32-2205-4ee9-931e-61afd2673962	459
Poa pratensis	335
280f1c3d-a245-4991-b933-3108e82305d1	287
flowers	231
e4093d69-c115-400e-bdb2-06f63b17a309	211
under Eucalyptus	189
ex. log	149
360134bd-0fc7-4ad7-bb29-ed8ae4150b1e	109
mud	94
Crow	90
grasses	89
salix	82
flower	82
tree	78
flowers of Leguminosae	78
under oak	74

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Ixodidae Koch, 1844	interactsWith	2c77dc27-d40d-450e-a5e9-2078ad9d2884	504
Mezira granulata (Say, 1832)	adjacentTo	under	258
Dermacentor variabilis (Say, 1821)	interactsWith	e4093d69-c115-400e-bdb2-06f63b17a309	205
Psammotettix	adjacentTo	Poa pratensis	202
Hypera brunnipennis (Boheman, 1834)	adjacentTo	under Eucalyptus	189
Haemaphysalis leporispalustris (Packard, 1869)	interactsWith	2f6ddf32-2205-4ee9-931e-61afd2673962	188
Ixodidae Koch, 1844	interactsWith	280f1c3d-a245-4991-b933-3108e82305d1	169
Hymenoptera	hasHost	Soybeans	153
Pulicidae Billberg, 1820	interactsWith	2f6ddf32-2205-4ee9-931e-61afd2673962	136
Dermacentor variabilis (Say, 1821)	interactsWith	2c77dc27-d40d-450e-a5e9-2078ad9d2884	122
Ptinidae Latreille, 1802	hasHost	ex. log	98
Diaphorinae	hasHost	Soybeans	89
Myrsidea interrupta (Osborn, 1896)	adjacentTo	Crow	89
Ixodes scapularis Say, 1821	interactsWith	280f1c3d-a245-4991-b933-3108e82305d1	81
Tetraloniella (Tetraloniella) donata (Cresson, 1878)	adjacentTo	flowers of Leguminosae	78
Chalcidoidea	hasHost	Soybeans	70

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Flexamia inflata (Osborn & Ball, 1897)	adjacentTo	Poa pratensis	69
Cynipidae	adjacentTo	tree	69
Coleoptera Linnaeus, 1758	adjacentTo	seaweed	69

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
```



```

CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
CLASS
  STYLE
    COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
    DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 3.4410664066392633
    RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
    OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
  END
END
END
END
END

```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These

alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
b530ce a a42 b1 b80b0c06cdb	NONE	col	b530ce a a42 b1 b80b0c06cdb
e45 a c fad a292826f5998	NONE	col	e45 a c fad a292826f5998
Ba1a3 cbd a7080571ba6b	NONE	col	Ba1a3 cbd a7080571ba6b
Db26d6 f1 f5c d c93e4a757a5	NONE	col	Db26d6 f1 f5c d c93e4a757a5

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	1647
col	class	7
col	family	178
col	genus	483
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	3
col	kingdom	2
col	order	26
col	parvorder	1
col	species	1273
col	subfamily	24
col	subgenus	18
col	suborder	7
col	subspecies	42
col	subtribe	1
col	superfamily	4
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	16
col	variety	3
discoverlife	NA	3655
discoverlife	species	18
gbif	NA	1670
gbif	class	7

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
gbif	family	178
gbif	genus	487
gbif	kingdom	2
gbif	order	26
gbif	species	1278
gbif	subspecies	56
gbif	variety	7
itis	NA	2216
itis	class	7
itis	family	177
itis	genus	350
itis	infraorder	1
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	29
itis	species	821
itis	subclass	1
itis	subfamily	26
itis	suborder	8
itis	subspecies	25
itis	superclass	1
itis	superfamily	6
itis	superorder	1
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	4
mdd	NA	3672
ncbi	NA	2061
ncbi	class	7
ncbi	family	174
ncbi	genus	434
ncbi	infraorder	1
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	26
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	898
ncbi	species group	1
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	subfamily	30
ncbi	subgenus	18
ncbi	suborder	7
ncbi	subspecies	18
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	4
ncbi	superorder	2
ncbi	tribe	5

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	varietas	1
pbdb	NA	3137
pbdb	class	8
pbdb	family	161
pbdb	genus	230
pbdb	informal	1
pbdb	infraorder	5
pbdb	kingdom	2
pbdb	order	30
pbdb	species	56
pbdb	subclass	1
pbdb	subfamily	34
pbdb	suborder	10
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	superfamily	5
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	tribe	5
pbdb	unranked clade	4
tpt	NA	3437
tpt	family	4
tpt	genus	20
tpt	order	1
tpt	species	210
tpt	subspecific epithet	1
wfo	NA	3428
wfo	family	4
wfo	genus	118
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	118
wfo	subspecies	3
wfo	variety	3
worms	NA	3181
worms	class	4
worms	family	121
worms	genus	180
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	kingdom	2
worms	order	24
worms	species	136
worms	subclass	3
worms	subfamily	11
worms	suborder	7
worms	subspecies	1
worms	superfamily	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
worms	superorder	1

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	2099
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2323
col	SYNONYM_OF	796
discoverlife	NONE	4379
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	1
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	17
gbif	NONE	2124
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2450
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	781
itis	NONE	2687
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1635
itis	SYNONYM_OF	103
mdd	NONE	4324
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	54
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	1
ncbi	NONE	2541
ncbi	SAME_AS	1854
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	76
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	8
pbdb	NONE	3690
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	687
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	56
tpt	NONE	4090
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	99
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	284
wfo	NONE	4076
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	64
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	272
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	40
worms	NONE	3753
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	622

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
worms	SYNONYM_OF	52

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T14:49:53Z	note	target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-06-03T14:49:53Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with id: [25] and name: [Localized to]
2026-06-03T14:49:53Z	note	target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder
2026-06-03T14:49:53Z	note	found unsupported interaction type with id: [25] and name: [Localized to]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
target taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder	20379
found unsupported interaction type with id: [25] and name: [Localized to]	17272
found unsupported interaction type with name: [PreviousCrop]	579
found unsupported interaction type with name: [A-C]	441

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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